

Surveys in Systems Research: An Overview of Sample Sizes, Response Rates, and Statistical
Approaches Utilized in Studies

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to identify typical sample sizes and response rates in survey research studies within the discipline of information systems, as well as the top statistical analyses utilized for survey data in these studies. 801 articles were identified from 27 top information systems journals that met the criteria of using a survey as the research method. The typical survey study received between 136 (first quartile) and 374 (third quartile) respondents, with a median number of 217. Typical response rate ranged between 16.5% and 50.0%, with a median of 27.8%. It was found that articles published in journals included in the Social Science Citation Index had significantly larger numbers of respondents than those not included in the index, though no difference was found for response rate. Structural Equation Modeling, including the Partial Least Squares approach, was utilized in the largest number of studies. The findings of this study are useful for IS researchers in developing appropriate procedures for survey-based research.

Keywords: IS Research, Surveys, Questionnaires, Sample, Rate

The use of survey methodology, or questionnaires (these terms are used synonymously in this study), has grown increasingly common with the emergence of web-based technology. From an administrative perspective, surveys are now one of the least costly, in terms of time and least, research methods, while still having sufficient rigor to be published in top journals in the information systems discipline. However, there are significant questions with this method as to what sample size and response rate is appropriate as well as what types of statistical analysis are best to analyze survey data. This study offers one solution to these concerns by analyzing the sample size, response rate, and analyses performed in over 800 survey studies published between the years of 2000-2019, providing the most common approaches across a variety of articles published top journals in the discipline.

Literature Review

Overviews of Survey Research in Information Systems

A variety of studies have examined the use of surveys as a research method in information systems-related research. Two studies, both released in 1993, analyzed the quality of survey research in IS in preceding decade. Pinsonneault and Kraemer (1993) identify five weaknesses in IS survey research in the 1980s: 1) utilizing only a single method (survey) when multiple methods would be more appropriate; 2) inadequate sampling procedures; 3) low response rates; 4) poor alignment of participants and units of analysis; 5) reliance on cross-sectional surveys when longitudinal data is needed. In regard to sample size, only 31% had a sample of more than 200 participants, while 44% had 100 or fewer participants. Nearly three-fourths of studies were found to either not report response rate or have a rate below

51%. The authors suggest that significant improvements are needed for the quality of survey-based studies.

Grover, Lee, and Durand (1993) looked at issues of MIS journals (MIS Quarterly, Information and Management, Journal of Management Information Systems, and Proceedings of the International Conference on Information Systems) published during the 1980s – a total of 173 articles. The analysis showed that survey research increased significantly in popularity from the early to the later years of the 1980s, with both the number of survey articles and percentage of total articles using surveys increasing. The researchers note that only 58.6% of studies provided a profile of survey respondents, while only 47.6% reported a response rate. They do not, however, provide information about the typical number of respondents or the response rate.

Falconer and Hodgett (1999) discuss limitations to response rate in surveys of information systems executives. An inundation of requests to participate in surveys/share data, limited applicability of the survey, and time limitations were all major reasons for non-participation. The researchers claim that, due to these factors, the largest response rate that can be anticipated for a survey of executives is in the range of 42-58%. One solution to address low response rate is to utilize multiple research methods as a source of triangulation. Gable (1994) and Benbasat, Goldstein, and Mead (1987) propose qualitative case study/observation-type methodology to support data from surveys.

King and He (2005) examined external validity, coverage error and nonresponse bias in IS survey research – issues that effect the generalizability of the findings – in top IS journals, including MIS Quarterly, Information Systems Research (ISR), and Journal of Management

Information Systems (JMIS). The researchers found that coverage error was not discussed in the majority of studies and nonresponse is rarely explained in detail. The researchers also note challenges with response rate range from 7.8% at the lowest (in Journal of Management Information Systems) to 89.0% at the highest (Information Systems Research). The mean response rate by journals ranges from 33.3% (JMIS) to 44.6% (ISR).

Sample Size and Statistical Analysis of Survey Data

Several studies have examined requisite sample size for specific statistical techniques commonly used with survey data. For instance, several highly-cited studies examine the appropriate sample size for structural equation modeling (SEM). Tanaka (1987) investigated the sample size necessary for latent variable SEM. Tanaka notes that, historically, two of the most popular methods for identifying appropriate sample size in SEM are the Monte Carlo method – a simulation-based method that can identify at what point a model begins to break down based on sample size – and the ten-times rule – that sample size needs to be at least ten times greater than the number of links pointing to any latent variable in a model. However, in this manuscript, Tanaka proposes a variety of entropic and factor analytic methods as well. Tanaka's short solution to the sample size question: it depends. "Fifty observations may be sufficient for a model hypothesizing a single latent variable underlying four measured indicators. The same number of observations will be inadequate for a model with 20 measured variables and four latent variables" (Tanaka, 1987, p. 143).

A meta-analysis of SEM studies by Westland (2010) noted that many had insufficient sample sizes (50% too small) in order to justify their findings/conclusions using popular calculations of necessary sample size. One solution that emerged with great force in the 21st century is the

Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling. As noted by Goodhue, Lewis, and Thompson (2012), the belief in PLS-SEM to handle small and non-normal samples led to acceptance of studies with unusually small samples being accepted in top IS journals (likely inappropriately, based on their opinion). In absence of a single appropriate model for sample size, several researchers have proposed their own novel approaches (Aguirre-Urreta & Ronkko, 2015; Kock & Hadaya, 2016).

While structural equation modeling is a statistical technique that clearly has great interest in information systems research, a variety of other approaches are still used to analyze data and each of these have unique constraints for sample size. With ANOVA (as with many other statistical tests), it is noteworthy that as sample size increases so does the likelihood of a statistically significant finding being obtained. However, as noted by Brooks and Johanson (2011) the real aim should be not the significance of the finding but rather the size of the effect. In this regard, an appropriate sample size can be found by estimating the anticipated difference between the populations being studied. Knofczynski and Mundfrom (2008) used 23,000,000 computer-generated samples to determine appropriate sample sizes for multiple regression, finding that, depending on the number of predictor variables and p^2 value, the appropriate sample size could range from 7 (for two predictors and very low confidence level) to over two thousand (for 5+ predictors and very high confidence). These studies are helpful in providing a reference point for minimum sample size for specific statistical tests but do not provide clear guidance based on the discipline (information systems) or method (surveys), as proposed in this study.

Research Problem and Questions

There is a lack of recent research on the use of the survey method in IS research. Over the past two decades, the administration of surveys has changed significantly, from postal mail distribution to web and email-based distribution. In theory, it is now both easier for researchers to reach potential participants and for participants to complete and submit the survey. This decrease in barriers to participation may have resulted in an increase in the typical and expected number of participants in survey research. The development and adoption of new statistical analyses – like Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling – may dictate new demands for survey-based studies. Little is known about the specific statistical analyses used for survey data and improved understanding will help guide future research efforts.

The following research questions were developed to guide this study:

1. What is the typical sample size for IS survey studies?
2. What is the typical response rate for these studies?
3. What methods of statistical analysis are most commonly used with IS survey data?

Methods

Using the Association to Advance Collegiate Schools of Business's ranked journal guide to select appropriate systems' journals, all articles were selected that contain the words "survey" or "questionnaire" in any field (title, keywords, abstract) and were published between the years of 2000 and 2019. This initial search retrieved 1137 results. Each result was then carefully reviewed to eliminate any book reviews, editorials, and any other studies that did not use a pure online survey/questionnaire method. This resulted in a final data set of 801 articles.

For each of the 801 articles, the following data was collected: 1) the number of respondents to the survey (sample size), the survey response rate (if applicable), and the methods of statistical analysis performed on the data. Frequencies were compiled for all three categories. Data was further divided based on whether the journal in which the study was published is affiliated with the Social Science Citation Index (SSCI). Journals included in the SSCI are often considered to have greater prominence and thus may be a bit unique from the “average” journal. Comparing SSCI and non-SSCI journals will provide insight into any difference in findings based on journal reputation. Results were also stratified to identify median response rate and sample size for each major statistical method.

Results

Shown in Figure 1 is the change in median sample size in survey studies over the period 2000-2019, overall as well as broken down into SSCI and non-SSCI journals. Table 1 displays the findings for mean, median, first quartile, third quartile, minimum, and maximum for each of the three groups. A Kruskal-Wallis H Test reveals a significant difference between the median sample size for SSCI journals (median = 217) and for non-SSCI journals (142). There is also a significant difference in sample for studies published 2000-2004 (median = 153) and 2015 -2019 (225). The correlation between year and sample size is .68, $p < .01$, indicating a strong correlation. From this data, it may be concluded that articles published in SSCI journals and in more recent years tend to have significant larger sample sizes than those published earlier and/or in non-SSCI journals.

Figure 1. Median Sample Size By Year for SSCI, non-SSCI, and All Journals, 2000-2019

Quartile ranges give some indication of appropriate sample size for IS survey studies. While some variation certainly exists, an appropriate sample size for most papers in top IS journals appears to be around 136, which is considerably larger than for non-SSCI journals at 86. A few articles have much lower sample sizes, as indicated by the minimum values of 23 and 15; however, only 50 studies had a sample size below 50 and most of these focused on a very specific and challenging-to-contact population (e.g., Chief Information Officers of Fortune 500 companies). The discrepancy between mean, median, and third quartile values demonstrate that exceedingly large samples are unusual. A sample size in the area of a couple hundred individuals seems sufficient for virtually all types of survey studies.

Table 1. Findings for Sample Size in IS Survey Research

Measure	SSCI Journals	Non-SSCI Journals	All Journals
Mean	420	356	396
Median	217	142	201
1st Quartile	136	87	116
3rd Quartile	374	321	368
Minimum	23	15	15
Maximum	12893	22488	22488

Table 2 shows response rate findings for survey studies. Across both journal types (SSCI and non-SSCI), the average response rate is quite similar. There is no statistically significant difference between the two groups ($H = 1.12, p = .29$). Generally, an appropriate response rate appears to be around 15-30%. Those studies that have a very small response rate (around

3%) typically involve a very large population, meaning a large sample is still achieved even with the small response rate. Studies with a small population, particularly in SSCI journals, have a very high response rate (often 80%+). Surveys are often distributed multiple times to achieve sufficient response rate.

Table 2. Findings for Response Rate in IS Survey Research

Measure	SSCI Journals	Non-SSCI Journals	All Journals
Mean	35.1%	40.0%	37.3%
Median	27.8%	38.5%	29.5%
1st Quartile	16.5%	17.1%	16.7%
3rd Quartile	50.0%	56.8%	56.1%
Minimum	2.7%	2.5%	2.5%
Maximum	93.0%	91.0%	93.0%

Displayed in Table 3 are methods of analysis used most commonly with survey data. Only a small number of survey studies (particularly very few among SSCI journals) use only descriptive statistics. The most common method is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), with the Partial Least Squares (PLS) variant used in 47% of these studies (or 19.8% of all survey studies). Tests of means or variance are used in 15% of studies, with ANOVA used in 6.7% of all studies, t-tests in 6.1%, MANOVA in 1.2%, and several other variants used in less than 1% of all studies. Parametric analyses are used more frequently than non-parametric ones (though it is unlikely that all of these studies that utilize parametric measures have tested for normality and other assumptions of the parametric methods). About one-fourth of studies used methods from multiple categories of analysis, commonly SEM and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) or Correlation Analysis and Regression Analysis.

Table 3. Percentage of Studies Employing Each Analytical Method

Method	Percent
Structural Equation Modeling (Standard, Partial Least Squares)	42.40%
Descriptive Statistics ONLY	15.90%
Test of Means or Variance (T-tests, ANOVA, MANOVA)	15.30%
Regression Analysis (Linear, Logistical, Hierarchical)	14.50%
Factor Analysis (Confirmatory, Exploratory)	13.10%

Correlation Analysis (Pearson, Spearman)	9.00%
Frequency Tests (Chi-Square)	4.70%
Cluster Analysis (K-means, K-mediod, Hierarchical)	1.20%

Table 4. Median Response Rate and Sample Size by Statistical Approach

Analysis Type	Response Rate	Sample Size
ANOVA	27.1%	200
Chi-Square	41%	183
Cluster Analysis	20.4%	196
Confirmatory Factor Analysis	36.1%	197
Correlation Analysis	32.8%	195
Descriptive Statistics	44.6%	106
Exploratory Factor Analysis	30.3%	174
Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling	37.4%	173
Regression Analysis	46%	235
Structural Equation Modeling	38.6%	255
T-tests	35.1%	146

Discussion

Generally, IS research appears to favor large sample sizes for survey studies, in the range of about 100-400 respondents for most studies. These numbers of responses allow for more significant statistical analyses (e.g., SEM) that may not be possible with smaller data sets. The typical sample size has grown over the past 20 years from an average of 153 in the first five years of the new millennium, to 225 in the years 2015-2019 (+72). This increase is more pronounced among SSCI journals than non-SSCI ones, though this can be partly explained by the low number of non-SSCI journal articles that used survey methods in the first few years of the 2000s.

Comparative to sample size, response rate is remarkably stable between SSCI and non-SSCI journals and across all years of the study. A response rate of about one-third of the population appears appropriate for most studies, while those studies with very large populations may suffice with much lower rates and those with exceptionally small populations may need a

considerably higher rate. There is no correlation between response rate and the final sample size (Spearman rho = .024, p = .761). This may indicate that, for most studies, what is considered more important is not response rate but rather the size of the final sample.

Structural equation modeling is clearly the most common type of analysis (beyond simple, descriptive statistics) performed on IS survey data. SEM is generally used for theory testing or development. It also incorporates many elements from other types of analyses on this list (e.g., CFA). The most common variant of SEM used for these survey studies is Partial Least Squares Path Modeling, which is a type of composite modeling that is more robust in working with non-normal data. As noted by Hair, Sarstedt, Hopkins, and Kuppelwieser (2014), PLS has grown substantially in its use in business-related research. SEM, being an intensive statistical strategy, may require a larger sample than other types of analysis.

While 15.9% of survey studies utilized only descriptive statistics, most of these studies used data where other statistical analysis would not make much sense. For instance, a survey of AIS members perceptions of the most pressing issues in IS – while it technically could use chi-square or ANOVA based on the types of data collected and demographics of respondents – probably does not add much worthwhile insight from supplying advanced analysis, then such analysis was generally provided (particularly with SSCI journals).

There are several limitations to note and opportunities for further research with this study. First, with the method of selecting “survey studies,” it is possible that studies that used the method but did not indicate this well in the article’s metadata were not retrieved through the searching performed in this study. This may have produced a deflated sample. Other elements of the survey research studies could be examined in greater detail, such as what populations

are being examined most frequently in these studies? There is also room to examine what theories are being used in these studies and how they inform and/or align with the method, data, and analysis. A greater understanding of these facets of research will likely prove beneficial to IS researchers as they develop their research and prepare their findings for publication.

Conclusion

This study informs a greater understanding of the use of survey/questionnaire research in IS. By enhancing knowledge of typical sample size, response rate, and methods of analysis, it helps supply a basis from which IS researchers may advocate for the soundness of their research approach and findings. While it does not definitively answer the questions ‘what response rate and sample size are needed?’, this study does look to previous research accepted for publication in top IS journals and offers a range of values that seem appropriate given the response rate and sample size utilized in them.

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